

EXAMINING THE VIEWS OF PROSPECTIVE TEACHERS ON TEACHER LEADERSHIP

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Abstract:

The aim of this research is to reveal out the views regarding the meaning of teacher leadership, the qualities that teacher leaders should have, the roles of teacher leaders, the effects to be teacher leaders, the obstacles of being teacher leaders and suggestions for being teacher leaders. Study is conducted via qualitative research method. Maximum variation and criterion sampling was used and therefore 26 volunteer prospective teachers were participated in the study. Participants mentioned that teacher leaders are very important in the changing world for not only leading the school staff but also help schools improve. As teacher leaders are significant, school principals should indicate shared leadership behaviors, provide an environment for teachers to use their leadership potentials.

Keywords: teachers, teacher leaders, leadership, change, shared leadership, technology

1. Introduction

People take place in different kinds of organizations in order to meet their needs, survive, and use potentials. All these organizations have different managers, therefore different management styles. With the rapid change all over the world, it is very important for all the people in an organization to collaborate for competing with others in order to be successful and gain profit. So, the leaders of the organizations are very important in establishing collaboration among the internal and external staff and play different roles and indicate different leadership roles such as servant, visionary, shared, ethical, symbolic, cultural, transformational, and charismatic. In order to adapt these changes, not only the managers of the organizations but also the whole staff should be aware of the changes and indicate different kinds of leadership roles to have learning and improving environment. One of the organizations that should adapt these changes is the educational institutions. In this regard, leadership especially teacher leadership is

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important for schools, principals, teachers, students. When considered from these angles, the notion of teacher leadership is often confronted in educational institutions (Koşar, Er, Kılınc, & Koşar, 2017).

Leader is a person who influences the people around him/her. In terms of education, leader is a person who influences the others by directing them. When schools are taken into consideration, school principals come in mind first. However due to the changes in schools which try to adapt the innovation, it is not enough to view school principals as the only leader at schools. In order to transform schools into learning environments and the center of change with powerful school culture, leadership should be shared and school principals should indicate shared leadership behaviors. In this respect, teachers who are one of the practitioners and initiators of change should participate in all the administration processes. Therefore, teacher leadership becomes important (Beycioğlu & Aslan, 2010).

There have been some differences between being a teacher and being a teacher leader. Barth (2001) in his study explains 10 different requirements for being a teacher leader: Teacher leader chooses course books and materials, he/ she shapes the curriculum, creates standards for student behaviors, gives decisions on directing the students to special classes; they are effective in preparing the in-service training and teacher development programs, effective in creating a passing system and permanent policies, decisive in the school budget, evaluate teacher performance, play an important role in the choice of new teachers and also administrators.

When literature is examined, it is seen that there have been an increase in the number of the studies done (Aslan, 2011; Beycioğlu & Aslan, 2012; Can, 2007; Demir, 2014; Kılınc & Reçepoğlu, 2013; Özçetin, 2013; Öztürk, 2015; Yılmaz, Oğuz & Altinkurt, 2017; Uğurlu & Yiğit, 2014; Yiğit, Doğan, & Uğurlu, 2013) regarding the teacher leadership but still the studies conducted by qualitative research method is lacking. Also this study is conducted via the prospective teachers who are assumed to be teacher leaders in the future; so it will be useful for them to think about how to become a teacher leader. The new role of the teachers is being a teacher leader; so it is important to reveal out what these new roles are. The results of this study gains importance in the sense that teachers can adapt the new education system. It will also give an idea for policy makers, school principals and teachers for training teacher leaders from the beginning of their profession and education. For this purpose, the following sub-aims were searched. According to the views of the participants,

- what is the meaning of the teacher leader?
- what are the qualities of teacher leaders?
- what are the roles of teacher leaders ?
- what are the factors that influence teacher leadership ?
- what are the obstacles of being a teacher leader ?
- what are the suggestions for being a teacher leader?

2. Method

2.1 Research Design

In this study, which aims to determine the opinions of prospective teachers regarding teacher leadership, the phenomenological research design, one of the qualitative research methods, was used. Phenomenological studies attempt to determine the perceptions and reactions of an event from the experience of individuals (Fraenkel, Wallen, & Hyun, 2012). In phenomenological studies, the researcher attempts to capture the uniqueness of events from the interpretive point of view and their analysis. In other words, the researcher focuses on phenomena in which s/he has knowledge of and is conscious of but does not have an in-depth and detailed understanding of (Büyüköztürk, Kılıç-Çakmak, Akgün, Karadeniz, & Demirel, 2012; Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2013) and aims to discover and define the meaning or essence of the participants' knowledge and experience. In short, the researcher tries to understand his/her experiences (Creswell, 2014; Hays & Singh, 2012). Therefore, in this study, it is aimed to reveal out the prospective teachers' opinions on the meaning of teacher leadership in detail.

2.2 Participants

Purposive sampling methods of maximum variation sampling and criterion samplings together in accordance with the design of the study (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2013) were used. Prospective teachers who have been attending the last class, namely in the last year of their education before graduation, and have been going to public schools for internship application at least for two months were preferred during the selection of the participants. It was assumed that the teacher candidates have the opportunity to observe the teachers from different aspects and thus would be able to provide a deeper understanding of teacher leadership in education. In addition, in order to provide variation among the participants, maximum variation sampling method was used. The departments, gender, ages are taken into consideration. Therefore, the study group consists of 26 prospective teachers. 14 of the participants were male; their ages were differed between 18 and 24. 1 participant was from Biology, 4 from Science Teaching, 1 from Physics, 2 from Turkish Education, 2 from Preschool education, 2 from Chemistry, 2 from Mathematics, 5 from Class teaching, 3 from German Language, 1 from French language and 3 from English teaching departments.

2.3 Data Collection Tool

In the study, individual face-to-face interviews were conducted via prospective teachers. Yıldırım and Şimşek (2013) point out that interviewing, which is one of the qualitative methods, is a very powerful way of determining the perspectives, emotions and perceptions of people. The interviews averaged approximately 60 minutes. Semi-structured interview form prepared by the researcher was used as the data collection tool in the interviews. The form was consisted of questions related the meaning, qualities, obstacles, suggestions of teacher leadership.

2.4 Data Analysis

Regarding the analysis of the data, both descriptive analysis and content analysis were used. As for the descriptive analysis process, a thematic framework was established with the conceptual structure of the research and the research questions, which were both regarded to be a framework. According to this thematic framework, the data was compiled meaningfully and logically. Then, the derivation was coded using inductive content analysis and the final themes were derived by determining the relations between the codes and the findings. The aim was to reveal out the concepts underlying the data and the relationships between these concepts. In addition, descriptive direct citations have been included to conspicuously reflect the views of those involved in the study (Türnüklü, 2000; Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2013). In the presentation of the data, the criterion for the selection of the citation was taken into consideration, such as striking (different opinion), explanatory (suitability to the theme), diversity and extreme examples (Ünver, Bümen, & Başbay, 2010).

2.5 Validity and Reliability

Validity and reliability are the two most important measures used to ensure the credibility of research results (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2013). In this context, the internal validity of the research was tried to be provided with the consistency of the relevant data of the data collection tool and the findings of the research, expert examination, participant confirmation, direct quotation of findings. External validity was tried to be provided by giving information about which method was used in the research and which pattern was used in accordance with the research method. Internal consistency was provided through the examination of the consistency of the results of the research and external reliability was provided through the detailed description of the data collection period and analysis. Codes and themes prepared for examining whether the generated codes and the generated themes were organized effectively; they were presented to two experts and necessary arrangements were made in order with the suggestions. For the themes and categories determined by both the researcher and the other experts, the issues of “opinion association” and “opinion separation” were discussed and necessary arrangements were made. For the reliability calculation of the research, the reliability formula proposed by Miles and Huberman (1994) as $\text{Reliability} = \frac{\text{Opinion Union}}{(\text{Consensus Unit} + \text{Opinion Separation})} \times 100$ was used. The matching ratio between encoders for the calculated calculation is .93 Reliability calculations over .70 is considered reliable for this study (Miles & Huberman, 1994). During the presentation of the findings, the direct quotations are given and the teacher candidates are coded as T1, T2, C 3, etc. T is used for “prospective teachers”.

3. Results

In order for them to be easily understood, the results have been categorized systematically under six different headings: (1) views regarding the meaning of teacher leadership (2) views regarding the qualities that teacher leaders should have (3) views

regarding the roles of teacher leaders (4) views regarding the effects to be teacher leaders (5) views regarding the obstacles of being teacher leaders (6) suggestions for being teacher leaders.

3.1 Views Regarding the Meaning of Teacher Leadership

The factual views of the prospective teachers regarding the meaning of teacher leadership are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Views of Prospective Teachers Regarding the Meaning of Teacher Leadership

Categories	Codes	f
Researcher	The needs of the students	14
	The needs of the parents	10
	The needs of the colleagues	5
Decoder	Revealing out the potential of the student	13
Analyst	The reason of the problems	5
	Behaviors of the people	3
Self-developer	Professionally	18
	Individually	16
Producer	Projects	10
Innovator	Bringing new into class	20
Communicator	Bridge between parents, students, teachers, administrators	14
	Field knowledge	17
Expert	General culture	15
	Pedagogic Formation	14

When Table 1 is examined, it is seen that participants defined teacher leadership as researcher, decoder, analyst, self-developer, producer, innovator, communicator and expert. The participants who defined teacher leadership as researcher also revealed out the needs of the students ($f=14$), the needs of the parents ($f=10$) and the needs of the colleagues ($f=5$), codes. Revealing out the potential of the students ($f=13$) was revealed out under the decoder category by the participants. In the analyst category, the reasons of the problems ($f=5$), behaviors of the people ($f=3$), codes are found. Professionally ($f=18$) and individually ($f=16$) codes are found under the self-developer category. In the producer category, projects ($f=10$), in the innovator category, bringing new into class ($f=20$), in the communicator category, bridge between parents, students, teachers, administrators ($f=14$) code, in the expert category, field knowledge ($f=17$), general culture ($f=15$) and pedagogic formation codes ($f=14$) are found. As it is seen, the mostly emphasized code is bringing new into class ($f=20$). Some of the participants' opinions related to the meaning of teacher leadership are given below.

“Teacher leader is the one who communicates well with her/his students, motivate them and is an innovator”. (T1)

“He/She is the one who has strong field knowledge, general culture and has pedagogic formation.” (T2)

“Teacher leader solves the students’ password; she/he leads and guides the students.” (T5)

“Teacher leader is the one who understands the needs of the students. She/He should determine these needs in order to verify all the processes to gain success” (T17)

“Teachers should renew themselves and follow the new developments. In order to be a teacher leader he/she must improve him/herself individually.” (T24)

“Teacher leaders should learn the new techniques and technology immediately. She must be the first who practices the new techniques both in class and at school.” (T26)

3.2 Views Regarding the Qualities which Teacher Leaders Should Have

The factual views of the prospective teachers regarding the qualities that teacher leaders should have are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Views of Prospective Teachers Regarding the Qualities which Teacher Leaders Should Have

Categories	Codes	f
Individual Qualities	Self-Expressive	10
	Extrovert	8
	Patient	7
	Calm	6
	Courageous	5
	Emphatic	4
	Curios	3
Professional Qualities	Trusting	23
	Open to change	22
	Visionary	20
	Sharing	16
	Entrepreneur	15
	Expert	13
	Divergent	11
	Simple	9
	Risk taker	7
	Competitive	6
	Smooth-diction	5
Use of body language	3	

When Table 2 is examined, it is seen that participants revealed out two categories which are individual and professional related to the qualities that teacher leaders should have. In the individual qualities category, self-expressive ($f = 10$), extrovert ($f = 8$), patient ($f = 7$), calm ($f = 6$), courageous ($f = 5$), emphatic ($f = 4$), curious ($f = 3$) codes; and in the professional categories trusting ($f = 23$), open to change ($f = 22$), visionary ($f = 20$), sharing ($f = 16$), entrepreneur ($f = 15$), expert ($f = 13$), divergent ($f = 11$), simple, ($f = 9$), risk-taker ($f = 7$), competitive ($f = 6$), smooth-diction ($f = 5$) and use of body language ($f = 3$) codes are found. As it is seen the mostly emphasized code is trusting ($f = 23$). Some of

the participants' opinions related to the qualities that teacher leaders should have are given below.

“Teacher leaders should be courageous; she should not get afraid of taking risk, in order to conduct all the processes she should have good communication with the environment, she must be entrepreneur, and provide resources both to school and class.” (T9)

“Today, one who struggles can survive. So to be the first and compete with all rivals can win the contest and becomes a leader in a way.” (T16)

“Teacher leaders should be trusting. All the people around him/her should trust his/ her in that she/he tells the truth, behaves fairly to all.” (T18)

“Teacher leaders should be visionary; should guess what will happen in the future, she/he should take precautions, she/he should therefore prevent crisis in class”. (T19)

“Teacher leaders should be open to change, if they are not, how will they be able to accept new techniques, methods; they should always renew their knowledge.” (T22)

“Can you guess a diffident teacher leader? Of course, not; if a teacher is a leader she/ he should pull all people behind him/herself, she must take risk” (T25)

3.3 Views Regarding the Roles of Teacher Leaders

The factual views of the prospective teachers regarding the roles of teacher leaders are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Views Regarding the Roles of Teacher Leaders

Categories	Codes	f
Professional Development	Current developments	20
	Observation	11
	Experience	10
Instructional Leadership	Facilitating teaching	9
	Participating into activities	8
	Project	6
Transformational Leadership	Usage of new technology	22
	Usage of new teaching methods	20
	Integration of international resources	15
Collaborator	Development	13
	School Success	12
	Problem Solving	8
Organizer	Social events	10
Formal	Social club activities	9
	Group presidency	6
Mentoring	Newly appointed teachers	18
Source provider	Knowledge	17
	Expertise	15
	Equipment	13

When Table 3 is examined, it is seen that professional development, instructional leadership, transformational leadership, collaborator, organizer, formal, mentoring, source provider categories are revealed out by the participants. Current developments ($f = 20$), observation ($f = 11$), experience ($f = 10$) are found under the professional development category; facilitating teaching ($f = 9$), participating into activities ($f = 8$), and project ($f = 6$) are found under instructional leadership category; usage of new technology ($f = 22$), usage of new teaching methods ($f = 20$), integration of international resources ($f = 15$) are found under transformational leadership category; development ($f = 13$), school-success ($f = 12$), problem-solving ($f = 8$), codes are found under collaborator category, social events are found under organizer category ($f = 10$), social club activities ($f = 9$) and group presidency ($f = 6$) are found under formal category; newly appointed teachers ($f = 18$) code are found under mentoring category; knowledge ($f = 17$), expertise ($f = 15$), and equipment ($f = 13$), are found under source provider category. As it is seen the mostly emphasized code is use of new technology ($f = 22$). Some of the participants' opinions related to the roles of teacher leaders are given below.

"What does a teacher leader do? He/She guides his/her friends; how? For example if newly appointed teachers come to school, she/ he is willing to help him/ her in case she/he easily adapts school. Teacher leader uses his/her communication skills for helping the colleagues." (T4)

"Teacher leaders in order to lead the others at school not only verifies his/her formal duties but also tries hard to improve all people cause his/her school become a learning environment. She/he affects the others in case all people try to improve both the school and themselves." (T8)

"Teacher leaders' one of the most important duties is to be a part of establishing strong school culture at school, that's she/he should motivate all to participate in all activities at school such as social events, picnics, kermis." (T11)

"If a teacher follows global issues, follow the different counties' practices about education and brings them to class, it means she is really a leader, today it is very important to be aware of all new thing around this makes the difference."(T13)

"Teacher leaders should be aware of the problems around and in the schools, so she/he must behave as a mediator to solve the problems." (T14)

"Sometimes teachers know a lot but unsuccessful while transferring the knowledge to students therefore teacher leaders should tell the lesson simple in case all students can understand." (T21)

3.4 Views Regarding the Effects for Being Teacher Leaders

The factual views of the prospective teachers regarding the effects to be teacher leaders are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Views Regarding the Effects for Being Teacher Leaders

Categories	Codes	f
Family	The style of growing up a child	15
	Economic facilities	12
Education	Selfless teacher	18
	The opportunities of the school	9
Social Environment	Friends	10
	The society grown up	7
Personal Characteristics	Ambition	19
	Focus on success	14
Profession	Choice	16
	By chance	13
	Love of the profession	12
Administrator	Support	17

When Table 4 is examined, it is seen that in the family category, the styling of growing up a child ($f = 15$) and economic facilities ($f = 12$) codes are revealed out by the participants. In the education category, selfless teacher ($f = 18$) and the opportunities of the school ($f = 9$) codes are revealed out. Friends ($f = 10$) and the society grown up ($f = 7$) are the codes under the social environment category. Ambition ($f = 19$) and focus on success ($f = 14$) are the codes found under the personal characteristics category. In the profession category, choice ($f = 16$), by chance ($f = 13$) and love of the profession ($f = 12$) codes are found. In the administrator category, support ($f = 17$) is the code revealed out by the participants. As it is seen the mostly emphasized code is use of new technology ($f = 19$). Some of the participants' opinions related to the effects for being teacher leaders are given below.

“First of all, all families are very important. The education level of the mother and father is very important also, because the child is affected by them, his behaviors, culture, education are all shaped by the families therefore, how the people are grown up is important, the habits you earned are important. If your family grows you up courageous, risk taking, innovator, creative, it affects all your life. So, teacher leaders are affected by the family.” (T12)

“If a person is ambitious, it is dangerous but at the same time it is useful, how? If you become a teacher leader it means that you are of course ambitious, it means you study hard to achieve, you pay attention to all things, you try to do whatever you need to achieve.” (T15)

“If you are really fond of your profession, you try hard to be the most important and successful person in your profession, so teacher leaders are assumed to love their job.”(T17)

3.5 Views Regarding the Obstacles of Being Teacher Leaders

The factual views of the prospective teachers regarding the obstacles of being teacher leaders are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Views Regarding the Obstacles of Being Teacher Leaders

Categories	Codes	f
Self-related	Not taking initiative	16
	Technological competency	10
	Burn Out	8
	Lack of self-reliance	7
Administrator related	Attitude	20
	Expertise	19
	Support	17
	Perspective	12
Student related	Unwillingness	10
Parent related	Obsessive	12
	Prejudiced	8
	Dunning-Kruger	6
Colleague related	Resistance to change	23
	Unwillingness to produce	16
	Close to learning	15
School-related	Work load	20
	Crowded classes	18
	Physical opportunities	15
Multi-roles	Mother/Father	10
	Spouse	8
	Teacher	5
	Other	3
Economy	Low salary	7
	Lack of equipment	6

When Table 5 is examined, it is seen that in the self-related category, participants revealed out not taking initiative ($f = 16$), technological competency ($f = 10$), burn out ($f = 8$) and lack of self-reliance ($f = 7$) codes in the administrator related category attitude ($f = 20$) expertise ($f = 19$), support ($f = 12$), perspective ($f = 12$) codes are found. Unwillingness ($f = 10$) is found under the student related category. Obsessive ($f = 12$), prejudiced ($f = 18$), Dunning-Kruger ($f = 6$) are found under the parent related category. Resistance to change ($f = 23$), unwillingness to produce ($f = 16$), close to learning ($f = 15$) are the codes for colleague related category. Work load ($f = 20$), crowded classes ($f = 18$), physical opportunities ($f = 15$) are the codes found under the school related category. Mother/Father ($f = 10$), spouse ($f = 8$), teacher ($f = 5$), other ($f = 3$) codes are found under the multi-roles category. In the economy category low salary ($f = 7$) and lack of equipment ($f = 6$) codes are found. As it is seen the mostly emphasized code is resistance

to change ($f = 23$). Some of the participants' opinions related to the obstacles of being teacher leaders are given below.

"If the people around you are closed to change, keeps the routine and do not want to change the style they have, it is very difficult to make them accept your ideas, views, wishes; so teacher leaders in my opinion mostly face with resistance to change, so they can not alter the perspectives, they have difficulty in doing something new because the others only see school as a place they teach and then go home." (T2)

"It is very difficult to become a teacher leader if there are a lot of parents who claim they know everything. They come to school and utter lots of things they do not know, this make teachers tired, they have to deal with people who teach their work to them, that's horrible." (T6)

"Teachers have many things to do, it is very clear. The system forces teachers to do many different things. When we go to school for internship, I witness that all teachers deal with a lot such as parents of the students, students that have difficulty in learning, high lesson hours; they even do not have any time to do extra things as improving themselves, spending more time on students." (T7)

"At internship school my mentor always tells me that if a teacher cannot differ his/her roles she/he can lose herself/himself in various roles; she/he tries to be a spouse, mother or father, she/he can be a child of a ill mom and has the responsibility to look after, so it is a very big barrier for a teacher to have leader qualities and become a teacher leadership." (T10)

"In the school where we go to practice, the classes are very crowded, teachers have difficulty in telling the lesson, dealing with each student for very long time, giving chance for each student to talk in the same lesson hour, so the only duty becomes to give the lesson and keep the routine." (T18)

"The most significant aspects of becoming a teacher leader is the attitude of the school principal. Teacher leaders have to take the support of their principals. If there is a toxic leader, namely very autocratic principal in a school, he forbidden everything, do not listen to his colleagues and does not give chance for other to participate in decisions. Therefore, nobody there has a chance to express him/herself." (T23)

3.6 Suggestions for Being Teacher Leaders

The factual views of the prospective teachers regarding suggestions for being teacher leaders are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Views Regarding Suggestions for Being Teacher Leaders

Categories	Codes	f
Providing Opportunity	Authority transfer	14
	Give courage	10
In service training	Courses	12
	Presentations	8
	Growing up equipped teachers	5
Support	Administrator	20
	Families	18
Perspectives	Society structure	7

When Table 6 is examined, it is seen that in the providing opportunity category, authority transfer ($f = 14$) and give courage ($f = 10$) are the codes. In the in-service training category, courses ($f = 12$), presentations ($f = 8$), growing up equipped teachers ($f = 5$) are the codes. Administrator ($f = 20$) and families ($f = 18$) are the codes under support category. Society structure ($f = 7$) is revealed out under perspectives category by the participants. As it is seen, the mostly emphasized code is the support of administrator ($f = 20$). Some of the participants' opinions related to the obstacles of being teacher leaders are given below.

"In order to have more teacher leaders, the school principals have to support them, provide suitable conditions for teachers to improve themselves as leaders." (T3)

"Families should provide good education for their children; if they try to grow up a child with different qualities, wide perspectives we can have more teacher leaders." (T9)

"If the school leader never transfers his authority to teachers how can they have the chance to learn the process?" (T12)

4. Discussion

As for the results of this study whose aim is to reveal out the views of prospective teachers on teacher leadership, it can be said that prospective teachers revealed out different definitions. As for the meaning of teacher leaders, all the participants' views about the teacher leaders are seen to be positive. The prospective teachers depending on the experience they had in the internship practices mentioned that teacher leaders should have some qualities such as being trustworthy, being open to change, etc. One of the most important findings of this research is that teacher leaders have different roles to verify. They not only do their formal duties but also they help their school become a learning community. When the results regarding the effects for being a teacher leader is considered, it can be said that teacher leaders' background which refers to their families, education, society they grew in are important. As for another striking result of this study is that there have been some barriers that prevent teachers from being a leader such as lack of support. Also, participants offered some suggestions for being a teacher leader.

The most emphasized definitions for teacher leaders are their being innovators, self-developers and experts. The other definitions for teacher leaders are the researcher, decoder, analyst, producer and communicator. Balyer (2016) in his study also indicated that participants defined teacher leadership as the people who have capability to influence others, share knowledge with the colleagues and trustworthy people. He adds that teacher leaders are the ones who communicate well with others. So, it can be concluded that participants believe a teacher who brings new technology, new methods, new techniques, new ideas to school, class or for all educational staff becomes a leader as he/she affects the others. Also teacher leaders affect the school culture and both the teachers and the principals work together to build a culture of learning. So teacher leaders are assumed to be collaborators. Therefore it could be said that teachers who create, learn and conduct what is new in the school and class, renews him/herself and who shares what he/she knows with the others are defined as teacher leaders. Prospective teachers said that teachers who are open to change and are not afraid of using new things are considered to be leaders. It can be assumed that teachers who are not afraid of taking risks, and courageous enough to compete with others, who sees the future in a way and take precautions from today are considered as teacher leaders by the prospective teachers. Of course, the schools, students and teachers are not the same as 10 years ago, everything changes as well as technology, behavior, perspectives. Therefore, if the teachers try to use the old techniques for teaching, it won't be useful for students and will restrict them, that's why teacher leaders must be open to change.

It is seen that teacher leaders have different roles but one of the most important roles of the teacher leaders is to be a transformational leader. Among the other roles, instructional leadership, collaborator, organizer, mentor, source provider are found. This finding of the study is also similar to that of the study conducted by Balyer (2016). In his study, Balyer found that being an instructional leader, creating collaboration and improving it, providing the professional roles of teachers, participating in the change process, coordination, motivation and communication are the roles of teacher leaders. Also in his study, Balyer (2016) found that teacher leaders are the ones who help newly appointed teachers resembles to the finding of this study. This can be concluded that a teacher who follows current developments, current researches in the world related to the profession, and try to adapt the strong sides of these for his/her school can be assumed as a leader. He/she should be the pioneer in class for motivating students and being a role model. Also, teacher leaders should try to cause his/her students or colleagues to indicate high quality performance. Additionally it is clear that one of the most important roles of teacher leaders are assumed to be influencers. With this regard, it can be concluded that teacher leaders have various roles that have different responsibilities, so they should study and work hard to be leaders. Therefore, it can also be concluded that being a teacher leader requires some responsibilities and time. Sometimes teachers feel themselves tracked among lots of duties therefore it becomes difficult for them find time to improve themselves, help others, learn new things.

Ambition, administrator support and teacher's being selfless and indicating organizational citizenship behaviors affect being teacher leaders. It was also observed

that families' socio- economic status and the styles, how they grow up their children, whether they love their profession and focus on success are the effects of being a teacher leader. In Uğurlu and Yiğit's (2014) research, it was also revealed out that, organizational citizenship behavior is affected by teacher leadership. It means that if the teachers indicate more organizational citizenship behaviors; it increases their teacher leadership behaviors also. Also, in Yılmaz, Oğuz and Altinkurt's (2017) study, it is found that school principal should indicate supportive behaviors for teacher leadership. In Can's (2007) study, it is found that administrator's support helps improving both the teacher qualities and the school. With this regard, it can be said that in the context of the effects of being a teacher leader, both the external and internal factors in their lives have an impact.

The obstacles that prevent teachers from being teacher leaders uttered by the prospective teachers are the work load, crowded classes and not taking initiative; also it is apparent that the attitudes of the administrator can be an obstacle for being a teacher, his devotion to authority and control prevents teachers. Can (2006) in his study stated that, work load, limited time, lack of supervisory support are the significant factors that prevent teachers from indicating teacher leadership behaviors. Overall, it is observed that there have been some barriers for becoming a teacher leader. Therefore, it can be concluded that being a teacher leader requires some responsibilities and time. Sometimes teachers feel themselves tracked among lots of duties therefore it becomes difficult for them find time to improve themselves, help others, learn new things.

In order to increase the number of the teacher leaders, school leaders' authority transfer is seen important. In this case, teachers should have the chance of experiencing to be an administrator and could improve their leadership characteristics. In Kurt's (2016) study, it is also revealed out that distributor leadership supports teacher leadership. So it can be said that school principals' distributor leadership behaviors are considered to be very important for teacher leadership. Beycioğlu (2010) also offered to take some precautions regarding new improvements and organize some education programs in school or district levels. Therefore, it can be concluded that, it is possible to increase the number of the teacher leaders by focusing on the shared leadership.

In conclusion, from a holistic perspective, most of the participants related teacher leadership with positive qualities; they claimed that teacher leaders should lead the others, help their colleagues, principal, students to improve their schools. So, the person who wants to be teacher leaders should have some qualities such as openness to change, being innovator, curious and creative. So, according to the findings of the study, for the principals it can be offered that they should prepare suitable and improving school environment in order to reveal out teacher leadership; they also should provide enough time, necessary educational resources and equipment. In order to reveal out the potential of the teachers they should participate in decision taking processes. In service training, activities for teacher leadership can be organized regarding the characteristics, professional needs and expectations of the teachers. There should be an increase in the authority of the teachers and their professional decisions should be respected. Additionally in order to reveal out the formal leaders, among the

teachers solidarity and cooperation should be established among the colleagues. Teacher leadership training must be implemented during teacher's entrance to the profession; it should also become formalized. Future expansive conversations are needed to be encouraged with educators, policymakers and community leaders to create policies and conditions that support teacher leadership to take hold and flourish in schools nationwide. For the future studies, it can be offered that different researches with different methods including other participants such as teachers, principals, parents of the students can be made.

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